

Checklist for Data Management Plans

Version 13

Swedish National Data Service

snd.se

(+46) 31-786 10 00

snd@snd.se

SND, University of Gothenburg,

Box 468, 405 30 Gothenburg, Sweden

SND

Svensk nationell datatjänst

2026-05-13

Table of contents

Introduction to the SND Checklist for Data Management Plans.....	4
Data management.....	4
Data management plan, DMP.....	4
Why create a data management plan?.....	4
Requirements from universities and research funders.....	4
FAIR.....	4
Writing a data management plan.....	5
The SND checklist and other checklists/templates.....	5
Checklist for data management plans.....	6
1. Overview.....	6
2. Protect the research data.....	7
3. Collect or produce the research data.....	9
4. Document the research data.....	10
5. Organize the research data.....	11
6. Budget for managing the research data.....	12
7. Preserve and share the research data.....	13

Date: 2026-05-13

Version: 13

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
(CC-BY 4.0)

Please include the following when citing:

Data Management Plan Checklist, version 13, 2026-05-13

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6424768>

Introduction to the SND Checklist for Data Management Plans

Data management

Data management signifies how to handle, organize, and structure research data and documentation throughout the research process. To facilitate management of large amounts of research data, and to avoid time-consuming work after the data collection process, it is important to have a structured plan for how to manage data during and after the research has concluded.

Data management plan, DMP

One way to make data management easier is to create a data management plan, or DMP, early in the research process. A DMP is a structured document that provides a framework for how to handle the data material during and after the research project. What a DMP contains depends on the research discipline, type of data material, and phase of the research process. How you manage a data material in a project may also develop over time as changes are made or new situations occur. This means that a DMP needs to be a living document to remain relevant. We recommend that you start working on your DMP as early as possible in the process, before the data collection begins, but you can, of course, also create a DMP for a project that is already under way.

Why create a data management plan?

By carefully considering various aspects of data management in the early stages of research, researchers can ensure that the material is well-managed throughout the research process. Creating a DMP is one way that a researcher can take control over how the data management during the research process, and to make sure that there are adequate resources to manage the data well, for example by budgeting for data management. As support in designing a DMP, this document presents the SND checklist in some detail. After this introduction, you will find the checklist, where you can check the fields that are relevant to you and fill them out as your research progresses. The appendix contains help texts that describe each field.

Requirements from universities and research funders

Increasingly, universities and other higher education institutions require, or strongly recommend, that research projects and other research activities have data management plans. What the DMP is supposed to contain, whether the HEI has a designated DMP template, or if the DMP should be registered varies.

Many research funders also require that grants applications contain a data management plan. This is, for example, the case with Horizon Europe grants. In Sweden, the Swedish Research Council and Formas, among others, require that a DMP is written for projects that are granted funding. This may also become mandatory from other Swedish research funders. What the requested DMP should contain varies between funding organizations and can subsequently differ from SND's DMP checklist. However, you can still use this checklist as support when you write your data management plan, or data publication plan.

FAIR

The FAIR data principles – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable¹ – are increasingly common as guidelines in the research community. The main purpose of FAIR is to optimize the reuse

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

of data by making it possible to find, understand, and use data. Making your research data and/or metadata FAIR will require a little bit of work when you prepare them and continue to work with the data/metadata until you have made them accessible. This work will be easier if you write a DMP and follow it, as a systematic approach makes it more likely that data become FAIR. A data material can be more or less FAIR, meaning that you can achieve different degrees of “FAIRness” depending on to what degree you meet the principles. You should strive to make the data material as FAIR as possible, e.g., by having plenty of documentation and metadata that a search system can use to help secondary users² find the material.

Writing a data management plan

Start by reading through the checklist to get an overview of what it contains. Identify which parts of it that are relevant to your research and then start writing your DMP by entering the information you already know. As the project progresses, you can add to, expand, and revise the DMP accordingly. Parts of the DMP that don't seem relevant or necessary to include at the beginning may be needed later, so remember to revisit the checklist several times during the course of your research. You can use the SND checklist as a template for your data management plan or as support when you outline your own DMP structure.

The SND checklist and other checklists/templates

We have based this DMP checklist on several international resources, such as templates, online tools, and recommendations from other research infrastructures, universities, and research funders. The checklist is updated regularly and now complies with the recommendations from Horizon Europe, which the Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions (SUHF) and the Swedish Research Council also follow. The SND checklist may differ from the recommendations in, for instance, design and terminology, but contains the same information.

² “Secondary user” is a common term from data archives/data repositories. In this case, a secondary user refers to someone who reuses digital data from a previous/another research project, or digital data produced by, e.g., a public authority, which may be used for research.

Checklist for data management plans

Version and date

[At some points during the research process, you may be required to send a copy of the DMP to funders or external parties. It is recommended to add a date and, for each update, a version number to the DMP, as well as to make a note of to whom you have sent which version and why. Save a copy of each DMP that you send.]

1. Overview

Project name	[The name of the research project.]	
1.1 Project description	<p>[A brief description of the project. For example, the purpose of the project and what research questions will be addressed.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> By collecting all information about a project in a single document, old and new project members can more easily find the information they need, instead of having to search for the information or trying to find out who may have it.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know
1.2 Primary investigator/researcher (person, institution, or organization)	<p>[The person, institution, or organization responsible for the material and the intellectual content of the project. If possible, enter a researcher ID, e.g., ORCID.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> It's important to know who is behind a project and responsible for its material and intellectual content. This also means that data that are made accessible can be cited correctly.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know
1.3 Contributing researchers and/or organizations and their roles	<p>[Other organizations and/or persons who are or will be involved in the project, including the participating research principal and possible other participating organizations.</p> <p>Describe how responsibilities are assigned in the research group (e.g., between the project leader, research staff, and technical staff), and who is responsible for what (who creates and updates the DMP, who is the project's contact, etc.).]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> If the data will be made accessible after the project, it's important to know who has contributed to the project. By assigning and documenting roles and responsibilities, it is clearer what is expected from each person, easier to follow up work done during the process, and new co-workers can see who does what, etc.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know
1.4 Research principal	<p>[Who or what organization is responsible for the research, and for making sure that an application for ethical review is submitted.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> The research principal is the authority, natural, or legal person in whose operations the research is conducted, e.g., a higher education institution, municipality, region, other public authority, or private enterprise. The research principal has the ultimate responsibility for the research and, if needed, applies for ethical approval from the Swedish Ethical Review Agency. If a research project has several research principals, one of them is responsible for applying for ethical review. (See "Guide to the ethical review of research on humans [PDF]" from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority.)</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know

1.5 Responsible department/unit	<p>[The organization with administrative responsibility for the project, e.g., a department at a university.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> This is administrative information that may be of interest for a funder or data repository. This information makes it possible to trace a project to someone responsible within an organization.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
1.6 Funding	<p>[Information about the research funding, e.g., funder(s), project title on the funding application, and the funder's reference number for the application.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> If the DMP contains information about project funding, it's easier to find the information when needed. Enter information about submitted applications and granted funding in the DMP or add references to the documents and where to find them.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
1.7 Guidelines	<p>[Information about relevant guidelines from the HEI or from funders, preferably with references to where those documents can be found as well as the document version used. Make sure that the documents can be accessed even after the project ends. If information later in the DMP relates to these guidelines, make a reference to this field.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Many HEIs/research organizations have local rules and guidelines that are important to be aware of. Some examples are IT security policies, guidelines for information classification, or a handbook for research documentation. By complying with these guidelines, you get some assistance in, e.g., how to adapt the technical, physical, and administrative environments so that the research material is securely handled. Funding terms & conditions may also affect the data management, for example by requiring open access to research data. One way to make sure that these documents can be accessed even after the project has ended is to save them in the project's document folder.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
2. Protect the research data		
2.1 Information security and classification	<p>[Refer to the information security guidelines and policies at your university/organization and define what implications they have. What information classification level does the data material have and what security measures are needed to protect the material? Who should have access to the project data during the project and how do you plan to protect the data from unauthorized access?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Access to the data material must be restricted so that authorized persons can access it, while it is protected from unauthorized access. Secure work and storage environments can include access restriction (e.g., passwords), encryption, and virus and access protection. You may need to contact your organization's IT security office to make sure that you have addressed all questions regarding information security before the data collection begins.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
2.2 Ethical review	<p>[Does the research require ethical review, or has it been approved in an ethical review? Enter the reference number from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority or other ethics committee.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Research that falls under the scope of the Act (2003:460) concerning the Ethical Review of Research Involving Humans</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>

(the Ethical Review Act) can only be carried out after ethical approval. Without ethical approval, the research is illegal and subject to legal consequences. Ethical approval from a regional ethics committee is also needed for research that involves live animals.

2.3 Confidential information	<p>[Does the material contain confidential information (see The Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act (SFS 2009:400)) that requires special treatment and/or limits the access to the material during/after the project? This can include personal data, military installations, telecom infrastructure, nesting grounds, or other types of confidential or classified data.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> If the material contains confidential information, you must guarantee that it's protected from unauthorized access. Contact your organization's IT security office to make sure that data are handled correctly for their information classification level (see 2.1 above). This classification influences which assessment should be made before research data can be disclosed to another party.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
2.4 Information about personal data processing to research subjects	<p>[Will the research project include processing of personal data? Depending on the data collection method, the research subjects need to receive thorough and transparent information about the data processing, including the research purpose and legal basis for processing personal data]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regulates on which legal grounds personal data can be lawfully processed. One requirement is that the research subjects receive thorough information about which personal data will be processed and how they will be processed. This means that the research subjects are informed about for what purpose and on what legal grounds the processing will be made. By providing this information, research subjects gain insight into and control over what information about them is processed. The Swedish Ethical Review Authority has templates for informed consent.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
2.5 Protection of participant identity	<p>[How will the research subjects' identities be protected?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Protecting the personal integrity of research subjects is a fundamental principle in research and an important ethical responsibility to the participants in a research project. Data that contain personal information need to be securely stored, in compliance with the guidelines at your university/organization.</p> <p>Research material may also contain sensitive personal data that need to be classified. Therefore, it's important to have routines for how to handle requests to access personal data in accordance with the principle of public access to information. When the project is finished and the data material shall be made available, it's also important to guarantee that the individuals in the data material cannot be re-identified through indirect identifiers in the data material. This can be done by de-identification measures or pseudonymization of the data, such as coding or encryption.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
2.6 Personal data processing	<p>[If the project will involve personal data processing, which reviews and documentation are needed to comply with the GDPR?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> GDPR regulates when personal data processing is allowed. If</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>

you will be processing personal data, GDPR stipulates that you assess and document the risk and impact on the research subjects' integrity, and that the general principles are followed and documented. Most higher education institutions have guidelines to personal data management. SND has information about [research data containing personal information at Researchdata.se](#). The Swedish Authority for Privacy Protection, IMY, also provides information for researchers: [Processing of personal data – for researchers \(IMY.se\)](#).

2.7 Intellectual property rights/copyright	[Are there any copyright and/or intellectual property rights to consider? Do you need permission to collect the material that is going to be used?]	Relevant to the project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know
	<p><i>Why is this important?</i> Copyright is protected in the Swedish constitution (Chapter 2, Article 19) and regulated in the Act (SFS 1960:729) on Copyright in Literary and Artistic Works. Copyright sets out a number of rights for the creator (author) of a work, and a number of limitations for the user. The Swedish Copyright Act regulates when and how the author's work can be used. Permission to use copyright-protected material includes consent, agreements, licences, and the permission to use material after the duration of copyright has passed (>70 years).</p>	
2.8 Agreements with other parties	[Do you need to sign agreements with other parties?]	Relevant to the project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know
	<p><i>Why is this important?</i> In some cases, you may need to sign agreements with other parties, e.g., if you will be using data from another organization than your university. If you enter into any agreements, document with which parties and where the agreements are stored. By documenting all agreements and what they mean, you can show funders and project members the conditions for your research project. There may also be additional legal requirements for agreements, e.g., from the GDPR.</p>	
2.9 Limitations to access	[Will there be any limitations to access other than those mentioned? Will there be any other rules for access?]	Relevant to the project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know
	<p><i>Why is this important?</i> Data producers or the organizations where the research is carried out may have policies that restrict access to the data during and after the project. It's important to be aware of these limitations and if any measures need to be taken to comply with them.</p>	
2.10 Embargo	[Are there any embargos on the material, or parts of it?]	Relevant to the project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know
	<p><i>Why is this important?</i> If a data material, or parts of it, is subject to an embargo (a limited period during which data cannot be made accessible), you need to make sure that the embargo isn't violated during that time. If you enter information about the embargo duration and reason for the embargo in the DMP, that information is accessible for all who work with the data material. An embargo can be temporary, e.g., while you wait for the outcome of a patent application, during which the material is confidential.</p>	

3. Collect or produce the research data

3.1 Types of data	[Describe which types of data will be used in the project, and whether they will be generated, collected, or reused data. Also describe the scope, quantity and, if possible, the file formats of the material.]	Relevant to the project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
--------------------------	--	---

<p>3.2 Existing data</p>	<p><i>Why is this important?</i> <i>Information about the data material makes it easier to plan for necessary hardware and software, and for possible staff needed to collect and process the material. Different types of data, such as numerical data (databases, spreadsheets), text, audio, image, video, geospatial, software, 3D data, etc., may require different resources for handling and storing the data.</i></p> <p>[Give a brief description of existing data in the field, i.e., data collected in previous research (including data from other researchers and research groups). If there are existing data, can they be used in the project? How will you document the origin of existing data? If you can't use existing data, give a reason why.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> <i>You should include an overview of existing data, as there could already exist material that can be used to answer the research questions, or some of them, but also to make sure that you don't duplicate a data collection. For a research funder, it may be relevant to know whether it's possible to use existing data material. If there aren't any existing data, it's vital to explain the value of collecting a new data material. If you will be using both existing and new data, describe how you will combine them.</i></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p> <hr/> <p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
<p>3.3 Data collection</p>	<p>[If you are going to collect new data, how will they be collected (questionnaires, interviews, observations, measurements, recordings, etc.), where, and during what period? Who will be responsible for the data collection? What resources will be needed during the collection process, in terms of staff, instruments, and software?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> <i>Data collection is a central, and often resource-heavy, part of the research process. By planning for how to collect the data, when they will be collected, and the scope of the data collection, you can calculate and budget for various resources. If you pay consideration to this in good time, a reviewer can more easily understand what type of data that will be collected.</i></p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
<p>4. Document the research data</p>		
<p>4.1 Documentation</p>	<p>[What type of documentation will be produced during the research project, and how will the information be structured? (E.g., in logbooks, variable lists, analysis plans, and protocols.)]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> <i>A research project produces large amounts of documentation, such as descriptions of the methods used, decisions, activities during the data collection, and detailed descriptions of the data. A systematic documentation of the data material creates conditions where data can more easily be published, found, understood, cited, and reused.</i></p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
<p>4.2 Metadata</p>	<p>[What metadata are needed to make sure that both the research group and future users can understand the data material, reproduce the results, and reuse the data for future analyses? Will the metadata be machine-readable?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> <i>Structured information that defines, explains, and describes data are called metadata. Metadata also make information machine-readable, so that it is possible to search for and identify it. The metadata documentation should be as thorough as possible and</i></p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>

contain all the information that may be needed to understand the data material. You should also consider how metadata are created and/or collected (laboratory notes, handheld GPS trackers, auto-saved files in various tools, etc.).

4.3 Terminology, ontologies, standards, controlled vocabularies, etc.

[Will the project use any established terminologies, ontologies, standards, or similar, to describe and document the material? Which ones? If you create your own terminology, will it be mapped against established terminologies?]

Why is this important?

Many scientific disciplines use specific terminologies, ontologies, and vocabularies (e.g., MeSH, ISCED, AAT, and ELSST) to describe, categorize and document data materials. There are also various standards that are recommended to follow (e.g., ISO 8601 for date, time, and time intervals). Using standards and established terminologies simplifies the communication between people in the same scientific field, but it can also make it easier to find material in, for example, journals. Sometimes, it may be necessary to create project-specific terminology lists if the existing ones aren't sufficient or suited for the project. If you create a project-specific list, you should do a mapping where you show which terms mean exactly or almost the same thing as in other lists, and which terms are unique to your list. By mapping terms against other terminologies, you improve the findability of the data material.

Relevant to the project?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

5. Organize the research data

5.1 Folder structure

[Enter guidelines for how you will structure the project's folders and, preferably, refer to a map of the folder structure.]

Why is this important?

A carefully considered folder structure with intuitive folder names is essential for a well-organized research material. This makes it easier for the project group members to find files, which will save time.

Relevant to the project?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

5.2 File formats

[What file formats will be used in the project? If possible, choose formats that are recommended for long-term preservation. Recommended formats are commonly used, well-documented, non-proprietary, and have an open technical specification.]

Why is this important?

If you choose a file format that is non-proprietary and platform-independent right from the start, chances are that you can avoid later problems with format conversion. It isn't always possible to choose a format that meets these criteria, as specific instruments, analysis tools, or developed software can affect the choice of data formats. However, bear in mind that every time a file is converted from one format to another, you risk losing information in the process.

Relevant to the project?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

5.3 File names

[How will you give files names in a systematic and consistent way, so that it's easier to find what you need? Enter guidelines that make it intuitive to tell files apart.]

Why is this important?

As the number of files can increase rapidly, it's good to think about and decide on a system for file names, which can then be followed throughout the project. This makes it easier to see which files have been used for what and what they contain. If several people will be working on a project, it's important to have

Relevant to the project?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

	<i>guidelines right from the start, so that created files are given names in a systematic and intuitive way.</i>	
5.4 Versioning	<p>[What guidelines for file versioning will you have in the project? Who will be responsible for maintaining, updating, documenting, and versioning a “master file” that follows the guidelines set up for the project? How will you be able to tell different versions of a data file apart?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Create guidelines to when and how to create new versions of data and documentation files at an early stage of the research process, to make sure that all project members follow the same principles. If the guidelines are clear from the beginning, you will have to spend less time trying to figure out which version of the data is the latest, which data have been used for a certain analysis, etc.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
5.5 Storage and backup	<p>[Where and how will the data material be stored, and how do you make sure that it is securely stored? Will there be regular backups of the files? How can the data be recovered in the event of an incident?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> You want to avoid losing your data material. Using secure storage with regular backups of the data is essential. You may want to consult with the university's/organization's IT security office about storage and backups before you begin the data collection/project.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
6. Budget for managing the research data		
6.1 Staff	<p>[Estimate what resources you will need to collect and document the data material during the project. This includes the cost of staff for collecting, processing, managing, and documenting the data during the project, as well as for preparing the data and documentation for long-term preservation and possible publication and access, which will improve the FAIRness of the data.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Handling and documenting data tends to require more resources than planned. By budgeting for staff costs for documentation and data management for the entire project, as well as for the work needed to archive and make the data available after the project, you are more likely to have sufficient resources.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
6.2 Storage	<p>[Possible costs for storing the data material during the project.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Data storage, for shorter and longer duration, can be costly, so it's important to budget for those costs as early as possible.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
6.3 Hardware and software	<p>[Possible costs for obtaining necessary hardware and software (e.g., systems for data collection and processing, backups, access protection, security, and documentation software).]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> With detailed and thorough budgeting and planning, you can procure adequate systems and software ahead of the project or make sure that they're in the budget.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>

7. Preserve and share the research data

<p>7.1 Prepare data and documentation</p>	<p>[Before preserving and sharing the data material, you may want to prepare the material. What file formats are suitable for long-term preservation? What documentation should be included with the data material after the project has ended? Are there any ethical and legal restrictions on the material, which mean that the data need to be processed (e.g., de-identified) before they can be made accessible? Where do you plan to archive and/or make the data accessible? Contact them in good time for assistance in how to prepare the material.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Digital file formats run the risk of becoming obsolete. If this should happen, future software may not be able to read and present the information in the files correctly, and valuable research data could be lost. Therefore, you should choose file formats that are more likely to remain usable in the future, i.e., formats that are commonly used, non-proprietary, and have an open technical specification. Another benefit of choosing those formats is that you won't have to convert the file formats at the end of the project. However, it isn't always possible to choose a format that meets all criteria, as specific instruments, analysis tools, or developed software can affect the choice of data formats. If that's the case, it's important to plan for how to guarantee that the data material can be preserved.</p> <p><i>When the project ends and the data material shall be made accessible, it may, due to ethical and legal limitations, be important to make sure that individuals in the study cannot be re-identified through indirect identifiers in the data material.</i></p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
<p>7.2 Metadata and keywords</p>	<p>[Think about which metadata and keywords you can use to make it easier for others to identify and find the project data when they are made accessible.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> By using plenty of relevant metadata and adequate keywords, you increase the chances that the data material can be found and understood by others for secondary use and new research. See 4.2 for more information about metadata.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
<p>7.3 Preserve and make the data accessible</p>	<p>[How do you plan to preserve the research material? Find out what rules your university/organization has for preservation and destruction of research documents and decide who in the research team is responsible for making sure that the official documents from the project are archived.</p> <p>What data will be preserved and/or made accessible, and how do you make that selection? Are there any local regulations? If it is possible to make the data accessible: when, where, and to whom? Will the data be made accessible through a data repository, a subject-specific database, at the university, or by the research group?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> Digital data materials need to be actively administered over time to make sure that they remain accessible and usable.</p> <p><i>Research materials created at a university/public agency must be archived there, in accordance with the Swedish Archives Act (SFS 1990:782). As a rule, official documents at universities and other higher education institutions shall be archived and it is, in</i></p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>

	<p><i>principle, unlawful to destroy official documents unless it has been specifically allowed, i.e., if there is a right to destroy or dispose of documents. Raw data files, ethical approvals, research documentation, and published results must be archived. If you have questions regarding archiving or destruction of documents, please consult with your organization's archive.</i></p>	
7.4 Responsible organization	<p>[Who/what organization is responsible for making the data accessible?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> The responsibility usually lies with the research organization or university where the research/study has been carried out, or where the researcher was employed at the time. In projects where several organizations/public agencies are involved, you must decide who will be responsible for making the data accessible, if they can be made accessible.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
7.5 Limitations due to guidelines or legal/ethical restrictions	<p>[Will the entire data material, or only parts of it, be made accessible? Are there any limitations, such as guidelines or legal/ethical restrictions that prevent the entire material from being made accessible? Do these limitations mean that you must take specific measures before the material can be made accessible?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> It is essential to sort out any limitations that may mean that only parts of the data material can be made accessible. Apart from the guidelines from funders and research principals, there may be ethical or legal factors that impose access restrictions. Making a data material accessible in the wrong way can be a breach of contract or unlawful, but it can also violate ethical regulations. For instance, if the material is confidential and individuals may suffer harm if their information is disclosed, or if secret information that may affect national security is disclosed.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
7.6 Limitations due to tools and software	<p>[Will a specific software or tool be required to use the data material? If it is: is it possible to add the software or tool to the data material, and if so, what documentation is required for someone to be able to use it? If it isn't possible to add the software/tool, what is required to be able to use the data material?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> To make it possible to continue using the data material, it's essential to enter information about what software or tools are needed, as non-proprietary software isn't always sufficient. Some tools may also be based on specific software and it's of great help if it's possible to include the software with the material, e.g., by open source code.</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
7.7 Data access rules and/or licences	<p>[Will there any specific rules or licences for accessing or using the material? If you will be using a Creative Commons licence, which licence and version?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> A licence can be used to describe the rights of the creator/author of the material, and under which conditions a work can be used. SND recommends that you choose/enable access that is as open as possible, in line with efforts on open access to research data from, e.g., the Swedish Research Council.³ Access may be</p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>

³ The Swedish Research Council (Vetenskapsrådet): [Open access to research data](#).

	<i>restricted if the data material contains personal data or other information that needs to be protected.</i>	
7.8 Local function for research data support	<p>[Contact your local function for research data support for assistance in making data accessible. These functions go by different names and are organized differently depending on their university/organization. Who in the project is responsible for contacting them, and when will you contact them?]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> <i>Many universities/HEIs have established local functions for research data support (Data Access Units, DAU) in collaboration with SND. These functions can help you make your data accessible, e.g., before publication of articles in journals that require that the research data are made accessible; or at a later stage in the project, when you may want to make larger datasets accessible. They can then provide advice and support in where you can make the data accessible, what you should think about, and what information it may be useful to provide.</i></p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
7.9 Certified data repository	<p>[If you plan to preserve or make data accessible in a certified data repository (such as SND), decide who will be the project's contact for the repository and get in touch with them in good time to find out how you need to prepare the data material.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> <i>A data repository can give you advice about suitable file formats, documentation and metadata, and other things that you want to consider when you prepare to make the data material accessible. If the data material and related documentation is in a format that the repository can accept, and in a format suited for long-term preservation, the material can be made accessible faster. Data that are made accessible in a Trustworthy Digital Repository (as certified by, e.g., CoreTrustSeal) are made accessible in accordance with the FAIR principles.</i></p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>
7.10 Persistent identifier (PID)	<p>[Will the material receive a persistent identifier (PID), and what type of PID? Enter the PID here if you have one, or when you get one.]</p> <p><i>Why is this important?</i> <i>A persistent identifier is a unique digital ID that refers to one or more objects, digital or physical. In research, it's common practice to issue a PID to publications or research data that are preserved for a long time and made accessible through digital resources. It's important to enter this information to show funders that you have thought about factors around access to the data material. As there are different types of PID, depending on e.g., field of research or where the data material is preserved, you may want to explore which PID is most appropriate for your material. Data made accessible through SND receive a DOI (Digital Object Identifier).</i></p>	<p>Relevant to the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>